

FEATURES OF PREPARATION AND TACTICS OF ACTIONS IN THE FIGHT AGAINST TERRORISM, BASED ON THE EXPERIENCE OF THE FRENCH NATIONAL GENDARMERIE

Golubenko Alexey Yurievich

Associate Professor of the Department of "Professional
Combat Training" of the Specialized branch of the Tashkent
State Law University of the Republic of
Uzbekistan, Associate Professor
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6514805>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th April 2022

Accepted: 25th April 2022

Online: 30th April 2022

KEY WORDS

*French National
gendarmerie, terrorist
organizations, tasks,
candidates, psychological
readiness, tests,
motivation, training.*

ABSTRACT

the article reveals the experience of the French National Gendarmerie in countering terrorism, the peculiarities of single candidate training and unit training, the methodology of selecting candidates for this elite unit is considered.

The process of globalization has covered all spheres of modern society. The geopolitical rivalry of the states of world leaders, such as the United States and Russia, has grown from cold warriors to the division of continents into their zones of influence and zones of influence of a potential enemy country. At the present stage, velvet revolutions are breaking out in the world one after another, often escalating into asymmetric conflicts of varying intensity. Evidence of these phenomena are the attempted coups in Belarus, Kazakhstan, the ongoing special operation of the Russian Federation on demilitarization and denazification in Ukraine. In all these conflicts, the interests of world leaders are clearly visible, and the development of terrorism often depends on financial support from outside and is directly aimed at solving the national interests of hegemonic states.

Uzbekistan advocates that the importance of military force in solving international problems should be minimized, and its functions should be limited to deterring wars and armed conflicts. However, taking into account the trends of global development, our military-political leadership is forced to adjust its vision of the role and place of military policy and military instruments. The availability of sufficient military potential, primarily modern and effective Armed Forces, becomes one of the conditions for its successful and painless integration into the system of international relations under construction.

In particular, the head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev regularly focuses on the problem of joint fight against terrorism at international meetings of various formats. Our President's contribution to regional security is also significant.

Thus, on September 29, 2018, at the Council of Heads of State of the Council of Independent States (hereinafter referred to as the CIS), he focused on the threat of terrorism: "The growing threat of international terrorism is of serious concern. Modern terrorist structures have significant financial resources, the latest information and technical means, have high mobility and efficiency. At the same time, the trend of their movement from the Middle East to Afghanistan, to the borders of the CIS, is gaining strength"[1].

The threat of terrorism is defined in a number of conceptual documents. The defense Doctrine, the Law on Combating Terrorism and a number of regulatory legal acts define terrorism as the main problem that requires the close attention of the entire world community [3].

From the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the fifth summit of the Conference on Interaction and Confidence-building measures in Asia held in Dushanbe, Tajikistan on June 15, 2019, "Problems of ecology, demography and migration, low standard of living and education are the main sources of social conflicts, a breeding ground for the spread of extremism and terrorism" [2].

In order to effectively counter the terrorist threat and counteract the destabilization of the internal situation in the state, a new power structure, the National Guard, has been created, combining a number of special purpose units whose main task is to counter terrorism. In the course of improving the tactics of actions of special purpose units of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, timely analysis, generalization, implementation and adaptation in the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan of advanced foreign

combat experience in the use of such units is essential.

In the EU countries, the terrorist threat has sharply escalated. One of the main reasons for this aggravation of terrorist activity is an increase in the poorly controlled flow of emigrants from the countries of the Middle East and Africa on the territory of which armed conflicts of varying intensity are taking place. The often reckless migration policy of Germany, France, Great Britain and other EU states allows a significant number of Islamist radicals and members of terrorist organizations, such as ISIS, Boko Haram, Al-Qaeda, etc. to seep into the flow of migrants. Upon receiving refugee status, terrorists, on the territory of the EU states, taking advantage of the tolerance of citizens and the intensification of the activities of human rights organizations, resume their terrorist activity. The intensification of the activities of Islamist terrorists on the territory of France is evidenced by a significant number of terrorist acts in the period from 2010 to the present, at least eight major terrorist acts with numerous victims have been committed. In order to counter the threat of terrorism in France, the intervention group of the National Gendarmerie known as GIGN (French Groupe d'Intervention de la Gendarmerie Nationale), (hereinafter referred to as GIGN), has been operating since March 1, 1974, is an elite unit specializing in combating terrorism and rescuing hostages.

As part of the French National Gendarmerie, GIGN has military status but perform police duties. Thus, the tasks of GIGN are broader than, for example, those of SAS. Gendarmerie operatives have solid legal training and are trained to negotiate.

Among the tasks are the arrest of armed criminals, in particular during hostage-taking, the fight against terrorism and hijacking of aircraft, the elimination of riots in prisons. This unit is assigned to perform tasks outside of France (for example, the release of hostages abroad) [4].

The complexity of the tasks solved by GIGN affects the organization of management and interaction of its units and fighters. Thus, the commander avoids operational directives during the operation and gives complete freedom to his two deputies and group commanders when performing tasks. Every serviceman who is part of the subgroups of the order of battle clearly knows his duties; experienced officers use young recruits based on their experience. Among the features of the work of GIGN fighters during operations is the use of gestures for communication and the complete rejection of verbal communication during this period. Special attention is paid to the analysis of the operation and the exchange of impressions after completing the task. During this, everyone analyzes their thoughts and reactions, comments or even criticizes the behavior of their friend during the operation. Despite the fact that criticism is not always pleasant, this discussion helps to act more successfully in the future.

GIGN is divided into teams, including an administrative group, four operational groups of twenty operatives, an operational support unit, including negotiators, scouts, signalers, snipers, dog handlers and special vehicles for transporting detainees. A special equipment group equips the unit with high-tech equipment [4].

All members are trained, which includes shooting, including from the air and

military equipment. GIGN members are rightly considered one of the best shooters in the world. It is for this reason that many similar departments have experience exchange programs with GIGN. Mental abilities and self-control developed by employees complement physical strength.

It usually takes three years to turn a green recruit into a fully trained gendarme GIGN. Any gendarme under the age of 32 who has expressed a desire to serve in the GIGN unit must have served at least five years in other units of the national gendarmerie corps before that. Preference is given to people from the squadron of parachutists and units for the suppression of riots in prisons. In GIGN there are officers who are responsible for the selection of candidates even during their service in other units of the corps. A dossier is collected on the candidate, his personal file is studied, conversations are held with the commanders of the studied serviceman. Only after that he is offered to qualify for the group. In the unit, it is welcome when the fighters themselves invite their comrades to serve.

However, everything begins only after permission is received from the commander of the gendarmes corps and the annual spring inspection is passed. Upon successful completion, the candidate is allowed to the qualifying round, which is based on GIGN located in Mondesir. Immediately after arriving at the base, psychologists talk to the candidate. Then he is offered various psychological tests to solve. In principle, this practice exists in almost all anti-terrorist units. Then follows the "qualifying" week. This test is essentially the same as the obstacle course for instructors of special forces units. On the first day, the candidate must pull

himself up 25 times on the crossbar, push up 100 times from the floor on his fists and with a weight on his back, perform the flexion and extension of the body on the press 300 times. As a rule, everyone passes this stage without any problems.

In the future, candidates will face more difficult tests. Candidates in full gear weighing 15-20 kg must run 8 km in 38 minutes, climb a seven-meter rope in 7 seconds, walk on a log blindfolded, swim 50 meters freestyle in 35 seconds and another 50 meters with their hands and feet tied, by the way, also for a while. Also, the course includes running on roofs, climbing a building through a drainpipe, escaping from captivity and survival, during which the stress response is checked. Another exercise is a fight with a guard dog from the cynological unit of the gendarmerie corps, specially trained to attack a person. During this exercise, the fighter's reaction to the attack is studied: whether he will be confused, how aggressive he will be. This test ends with another test of resilience and aggressiveness, during which each candidate must prove himself in the ring. Such fights are not held often, but they help to select those candidates who have a higher motivation to enroll in the group.

The most difficult stage of selection in GIGN is the third - the firing stage. During the passage of this stage, as a rule, about 40% of applicants are eliminated. To perform a shooting exercise, the candidate is given ten rounds. During the firing stage, the candidate is required to score 80 points out of 100 when firing a pistol at targets at a range of 25 meters. With a rifle, you need to hit the target from a distance of 200 meters and score at least 75 points. At the same time, the shooter is constantly in

motion. The best result is decisive for the candidate in the group.

After the selection is completed, senior GIGN officers or the commander personally conduct an interview with candidates, evaluate their psychological abilities. Selection practice shows that no more than 10% of the initial composition of candidates for GIGN pass all the tests.

Candidates who have passed the tests are enrolled in the cadets of the training center. They have yet to prove that they will be able to serve in the GIGN group. Cadets leave their units for three months to undergo an intensive course of physical training, which includes overcoming obstacles, self-defense and attack techniques, mountain-altitude training and swimming. They study tactical training, hand-to-hand combat, helicopter landing, demolition, mountain climbing, diving training. Under the guidance of experienced instructors, they improve their skills in shooting from a pistol, a submachine gun and an automatic rifle. During the performance of these exercises, both individually and as part of a group, penetration into the building and its inspection are practiced, with the development of elements of high-speed shooting. The speed of the exercises is constantly increasing, this allows instructors to study their subordinates under stress.

Within three months, instructors will have to determine the cadets who have passed the main course of study, and those who will have to pass the test for the next year.

After three months, the candidate is awarded a personal weapon and a sniper rifle FR-F1. During the next course, candidates develop and consolidate the acquired skills during complex classes and

exercises. This course lasts from 6 to 9 months and, in fact, turns the candidate into a fighter. During the course, they study the tactics of combat in the city, buildings, methods of penetration into various objects, the release of hostages. All training takes place against the background of maximum physical exertion. Intensive fire training in the dynamics of actions, performing an exercise from a sniper rifle involves hitting a moving target at a range of 200 meters in two seconds from the start of the exercise, allows you not to have regular snipers in the group. Anyone can be a sniper.

Even during the selection process, the most prepared candidates can be included in the GIGN support group when the group performs real combat operations.

Candidates who have successfully passed all stages of training are accepted into the group, in the presence of all personnel they are handed a cockade - the symbol of GIGN [5].

Two GIGN groups are constantly on round-the-clock combat duty. The time of readiness of the groups to perform the task is thirty minutes from the moment of making a decision at the headquarters of the national gendarmerie and giving orders on the use of the units of the group.

During its 30-year history, GIGN has conducted more than 700 operations against terrorists and criminals. During this time, GIGN lost 8 employees.

The highly successful experience of using GIGN units allows us to draw a number of conclusions necessary for consideration in order to improve the selection, training of military personnel in special purpose units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as making certain changes in the organization and tactics of actions during counterterrorist operations. The success of the tasks performed by the special purpose unit largely depends on the qualitatively constructed methods and criteria of the selection of candidates.

References:

1. Festive congratulations to the defenders of the Motherland, in honor of the 22nd anniversary of the formation of the Armed Forces of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan published on the website <https://www.norma.uz>. (Accessed 18.01.2014);
2. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the fifth summit of the Conference on Interaction and confidence-building measures in Asia, published on the website uza.uz/politic (Accessed 12.03.2022);
3. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan" published on the website lex.uz / docs Chapter 2. Section 2. Item 6 dated January 9, 2018 (Accessed 10.03.2022);
4. GIGN - Wikipedia. <http://ru.m.wikipedia.org>. (Accessed 19.03.2022);
5. GIGN Intervention Group of the National Gendarmerie, website military-informant.com. (Accessed 03/24/2022)